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Embedding Electronics Inside Metal with Laser Metal Deposition

Syed Muhammad Raza^{a*}, Zidu Li^b, Bhaskar Choubey^b, Martin Manns^a

^aPROTECH – Institut für Produktionstechnik, Universität Siegen, Paul-Bonatz-Straße 9-11, 57076 Siegen, Germany

^bChair of Analogue Circuits and Image Sensors, Universität Siegen, Hölderlinstraße 3, 57076 Siegen, Germany

* Corresponding author. Tel.: +49 271 740 2283. E-mail address: syed.raza@uni-siegen.de

Abstract

Laser metal deposition (LMD) is an additive manufacturing technology that allows layer by layer fabrication on existing metal parts. Integration of sensors inside the recipient sheet metals with LMD may result in smart components with enhanced functionalities, which would lead to machine tools with inherent sensing capabilities. However, special measures are necessary to prevent typical sensors from being damaged by excessive heat produced because of LMD. This work presents results of an experiment performed to embed electronic device, also known as microdevice, such as photodiodes, inside sheet metal with LMD. Results show the level of degradation of material and electronic performance after being embedded inside metal. The presented method of integrating electronics inside metal shows potential for developing multifunctional components while providing structural integrity for high performance industry such as automotive and aerospace. Future work will focus on developing insulation method and optimizing thermal management of sensors being welded inside metal.

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1. Introduction

Progress in integrated circuit (IC) technology is enhancing the production of sensor systems, such as image sensors and microelectromechanical system (MEMS) sensors, while enabling versatility and compactness in designing electronic devices [1]. Advancements in IC fabrication is empowering greater efficiency in photodetectors and more storage possibilities in memory system [2]. These innovations contribute to the development of high-performance electronics, supporting applications in sensing and data processing within modern technological systems [3].

The advancements in sensor technology is significantly driving progress in current manufacturing [4]. High-precision sensors facilitate real-time monitoring, improving process efficiency and product quality through data-driven decision-making. The integration of sensors in manufacturing units support production, thus reducing increasing productivity overall [5]. Furthermore, sensors combined with machine

learning algorithms enable automated systems to adapt and optimize their performance autonomously in an efficient manner [6]. These breakthroughs impact significantly to sustainable and resilient manufacturing by minimizing downtime, material waste and maintenance cost [7]. Overall, sensor technology has become an integral part of contemporary industry, promoting more intelligent and efficient manufacturing practices [8].

Laser metal deposition (LMD) is an advanced additive manufacturing technology that enables precise metal deposition on existing metallic surfaces [9]. Metallic powder is fused with high energy laser beam on substrate that builds up layers incrementally [10]. LMD has significant advantages in contrast to other additive manufacturing technologies, such as precise control over microstructure, five axis movement, and the ability to repair or modify existing metallic components [11,12]. The applications may extend across various industries, such as aerospace, automotive, and tool manufacturing. High precision and versatile manufacturing methods through LMD

enable the fabrication of customized structures with complex geometries [13].

LMD shows promising capabilities for integrating electronic devices within metal structures near functional surfaces [14]. Utilizing LMD to encapsulate sensors within metallic parts while preserving their functionality under operational conditions may particularly be advantageous for fabricating smart components and tools, enhancing the monitoring of manufacturing systems in real time, and expanding the scope of predictive maintenance, supporting resilient and flexible manufacturing.

2. State of the art

Photodiodes, based on amorphous silicon (a-Si), demonstrate a wide range of applications in imaging sensors. Müller et al. report an amorphous silicon based intrinsic photomixing detector (IPD). The generated photocurrent is proportional to the mixing of two optical modulation envelope functions nonlinearly [15]. Li et al. integrate a memristor with an amorphous silicon-based avalanche photodiode structure. The memristor operates in a volatile switching mode, serving as a passive quenching circuit to control quenching in Geiger mode [16]. Panda et al. show that by adjusting the doping concentration and layer thickness, the breakdown voltage in a-Si-based photodiodes can be tuned, achieving a lower breakdown voltage suitable for Geiger mode operation [17].

Various additive manufacturing techniques are employed to embed electronics and sensors inside metal near functional surfaces. Lehmus et al. present a detailed survey on links between additive manufacturing and sensor integration [18]. Hyer et al. propose a novel method to embed thermocouples in stainless steel with laser powder bed fusion to measure temperature over the functional surface. The embedded thermocouple survives the additive manufacturing process and demonstrates comparable performance to a non-embedded thermocouple during thermal testing up to 500 °C. However, a minor variation in response time is observed that attributes to differences in mass and the resulting thermal time constants [19,20]. Similarly, Maier et al. embed optical fiber sensors based on fiber Bragg grating strain sensors inside metal. The fiber embedding approach involves inserting a fiber component by substituting a removable "place-holder" component during a pause in the build process [21]. Petrat et al. combine selective laser melting and laser metal deposition to embed electronic components inside metal. The electronic device is prevented from destruction by correct placement, precise building strategy and regulated energy inputs for parameter sets in the manufacturing process [14].

With LMD, Ostolaza et al propose a methodology for embedding electronic components into hot stamping tooling for measuring temperature [22]. For successful integration of sensors, adaptive process parameters and low energy inputs are essential in order to prevent sensorial components from being damaged. Since the thermal nature of the LMD poses a challenge to embed heat sensitive electronic devices, Arrizubieta et al develop a thermal model that ease parameterization and anticipate the behavior of LMD process by material addition and determining the clad geometry [23].

The numerical modeling of LMD process proves to be a suitable tool for achieving close to optimal parameters. Utilizing LMD, Manns et al. conduct a principle test to embed optical fiber inside metal beneath functional surfaces and identify suitable deposition scan speed [24]. The optical fiber is sheathed with ceramic sleeve so as to prevent it from being damaged with excessive heat and embedded inside sheet metal with the proposed methodology. Building on previous work, Raza et al. advance the field by optimizing LMD parameters specifically for the embedding of optical fibers within sheet metal [25]. The approach focuses on improving process variables, such as laser power, scanning speed, and surface power density, to ensure the successful integration of optical fibers while preserving their light propagation properties. Later, the optimized parameters are validated to enable manufacturing of metal components with embedded sensing capabilities especially for smart tooling.

To the best of our knowledge, no evident studies report embedding custom-made microelectronic devices, such as photodiode, within metal structures with LMD. This lack of findings highlights a significant research gap in the literature, indicating an unexplored area with substantial potential for advancing the integration of microelectronics in metallic components with additive manufacturing processes for smart tooling.

3. Objective

This work is a part of an extensive study that introduce a novel method for embedding custom-designed microdevice directly beneath the metal surfaces of objects using laser metal deposition, while maintaining the operational integrity and physical properties of the device. Sheet metal components are utilized for experimental validation of the proposed approach.

4. Methodology

4.1. Fabrication of Micro Device

Fig. 1. Steps to fabricate photodiode.

A silicon wafer is used as the substrate for photodiode fabrication. A plasma-enhanced chemical vapor deposition (PECVD) system is employed for depositing the amorphous silicon and contact layers. Following deposition, standard positive ultraviolet (UV) photolithography process is used to pattern the structure, and an etching process is applied to complete the final structure. Steps involved in fabricating photodiode are depicted in Fig. 1.

4.2. Embedding Electronic Device with Suitable Parameters

Fig. 2. Steps to embed photodiode within a metal.

The approach to embed microdevices is adapted from Manns et al. that propose unique method to embed optical fiber cable inside sheet metal [24]. Initially, two metal sheets are laser cut: (i) the base sheet for embedding the electronic device and (ii) the sheet intended to be placed on top of the electronic device. Sidewalls are fabricated with LMD corresponding to the dimensions of the device, creating a slot to house them securely (see Fig. 2(a)). The microdevice is then placed within this slot as shown in Fig. 2(b). A metal strip is subsequently positioned over the microdevice to protect it from direct exposure of the laser (see Fig. 2(c)). Finally, metal powder is deposited onto the metallic strip, successfully encapsulating the electronic device within the metal structure, as depicted in Fig. 2(d). No additional heat protection measures are employed during the embedding process. Overall illustration of the experiment is depicted in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Illustration of the experiment

4.3. Visual Analysis of the Embedded Electronic Device

In order to assess the thermal impact of LMD on the microdevice, the embedded device is extracted by abrading the deposited metallic layer with a vertical spindle grinding

machine while using water as a coolant. The ejected device is subsequently examined under a stereo microscope.

4.4. Parametric Analysis of the Embedded Integrated Circuits

The photodiode samples are placed at the center of the probe station, with two probe arms contacting the diode. A semiconductor analyzer is used to record the current - voltage characteristics of the photodiode under dark and illuminated conditions.

5. Experimental Setup

A cleaned silicon substrate with an 85 nm SiO₂ layer is selected to be used as the substrate for the photodiode fabrication. The whole layers of these photodiode are deposited in an MVSystems multi-chamber PECVD system. Firstly, the ZnO:Al, a transparent conductive material, is deposited in the sputtering chamber of this deposition system. Afterwards, the P, I and N layers of amorphous silicon are deposited by utilizing silane (SiH₄) for all layers. P layer is the amorphous silicon with boron doped as p-type semiconductor. I layer is the amorphous silicon without any doping also as intrinsic semiconductor. N layer is the amorphous silicon with phosphorus doped as n-type semiconductor. As for the two-doping layer, P and N, are with additional phosphine (PH₃) and diborane (B₂H₆) respectively. Then again, the sample is back to the sputtering chamber and the ZnO:Al again is sputtered. During this whole process, the sample is kept in vacuum condition.

Electronic device is patterned by UV lithography. The positive photoresist AZ5214E is used to create the pattern mask. Then the ZnO:Al is etched using hydrochloric acid. The amorphous silicon is etched by reactive ion etching performed with SF₆ and Ar gases. The diameter of the structured photodiode is with 500 μm. The quadratic photo sensor chip is fabricated which yields the size of approximately 3 mm and the height of 1 mm.

The method for embedding electronic devices by LMD is

tested with the Trumpf TruLaser Cell 3000, Trumpf Laser

Fig. 4. Experimental Setup for LMD

TruDisk 4001, and a multijet process nozzle SO16. The 2 mm nozzle is positioned at a height of 16 mm from the substrate. Helium and argon are utilized as the nozzle and carrier gases, respectively. Martensitic high-chromium stainless steel powder, Metco 42C by Oerlikon, is used for deposition, with

its chemical composition detailed in Table 1 For the experiment, a 3 mm thick S235JRC (1.0122) structural steel sheet is used as the substrate, and a 1 mm SS316L stainless steel sheet is placed over the photodiodes, marked with red circles in Fig. 4. The base substrate is fixed to a metal frame using a clamp and screws to ensure stability throughout the LMD process as depicted with green circles in Fig. 4.

Table 1. Chemical composition of metal powder [25].

	C	Cr	Fe	Mn	Ni	P	S	Si
%	0.18	16.22	80.91	0.06	1.59	0.006	0.012	0.70

The device is encapsulated inside metal through LMD with parameters proposed by Raza et al for embedding optical fiber inside metal [25]. The LMD parameters are delivered in Table 2. The device is ejected by grinding the LMD surface with ATM Saphir 350E. To examine thermal impairments of photodiode, Leica MZ 7.5 stereo microscope is utilized.

Table 2. LMD process parameters [25].

	S235JRC	SS316L
Laser power (W)	500	90
Laser spot diameter (mm)	2	1.28
Surface power density (W/mm ²)	207	72
Scan speed (m/min)	0.30	0.20
Nozzle gas flow (L/min)	10	10
Carrier gas flow (L/min)	10	10
Powder feed rate (g/min)	10	10

To test integrity of the photodiode chip, the microdevice is analyzed by Keithley 4200-SCS parameter analyzer. Suss Microprobe Station is used with probes to connect anode and cathode with a voltage sweep from 0V to 1V with a step of 0.05V.

6. Result

Fig. 5. Photodiode embedded with LMD

The photodiode is successfully embedded within the metal while retaining its sensitivity to light thus preserving its functionality following the LMD process (see Fig. 5, marked with red squares). The welded surface extends 3.1 mm above the substrate and measures 7 mm in width on each side. The end surface is rough and requires post-processing to achieve a finished quality. However, this step is not performed for the purposes of this experiment.

Fig. 6 presents microscopic images of the photodiode embedded within metal using the LMD process. A comparison

between Fig. 6(a) and Fig. 6(b) clearly indicates that the LMD

Fig. 6. Microscopic images of photodiode (a) before LMD, (b) after LMD, (c) showing burn marks and (d) showing abrasion marks

process leaves noticeable burn marks on the photodiode. Similar burn marks are visible in Fig. 6(c) marked with red marker. The abrasion marks observed on the photodiode chip in Fig. 6(d) are caused during its extraction from the metal following the LMD process.

Current – Voltage characterization curve of photodiode is shown in Fig. 7. Before the LMD process, the sample display

Fig. 7. Current - Voltage characterization of photodiode (a) before LMD process and (b) after LMD process.

standard photodetector behavior, with a threshold voltage around 0.6 V. The photodiode demonstrates light sensitivity, as shown in the red line in Fig. 7(a). After the LMD process, a sample is cleaned again and characterized under the same conditions as before. Fig. 7(b) shows that the sample still functions as a photodiode, remaining sensitive to light, as indicated by the increased current under illumination. However, the current levels in both dark and illuminated conditions are noticeably lower than before.

7. Discussion

The results demonstrate that, with LMD, electronic devices such as photodiodes can be successfully embedded closely beneath metal surfaces while preserving their core functionality and light sensitivity. However, a reduction in overall current response under both dark and illuminated conditions is witnessed. This performance change may have resulted from

several factors related to the thermal and mechanical impacts of the LMD process on the material properties and structure of photodiode.

High temperatures inherent to LMD may have introduced thermal stress or microstructural alterations within the photodiode material, potentially impacting charge carrier mobility or creating defect sites that trap carriers. Such thermal effects can impair current conduction, reducing the sensitivity of the photodiode.

Additionally, the LMD process might have affected contact integrity or may have increased resistance within the diode structure. Higher series resistance restricts the current flow, particularly under illumination, where higher current levels are typically anticipated.

Furthermore, the metallic powder from the LMD process intruded the metallic strip intended to shield the photodiode, most likely due to tiny gaps present between the sidewalls and the metallic strip, which allowed powder entry. Consequently, the heated powder particles made contact with the photodiode chip, resulting in burn marks on its surface. Residue from the LMD process may also have led to surface contamination or oxidation on the photodiode. Such contaminants possibly introduce recombination sites or obstruct carrier collection, potentially contributing to the observed reduction in current response. Consequently, enhanced thermal protection is required to shield the photodiode from direct exposure to the high temperatures associated with the LMD process and from direct contact with hot metal microparticles.

Detailed post investigation with additional electrical testing and further microscopic examination is required to understand the change in characteristics of photodiode after LMD. The photodiode is removed with a semi-automatic vertical grinding machine, which resulted in scratches on portions of the chip and caused damage to the photodiode. An improved method must be employed for post-embedding examination of the photodiode chip to minimize potential damage.

The end surface generated by the LMD process exhibits a notable degree of roughness, primarily due to the welding procedure involving the microelectronic device and the use of a comparatively large nozzle. This larger nozzle size may result in less precise material deposition on micro substrate, contributing to irregularities and increased surface texture. Deposition pattern of nozzle and the micro-scale structure of the electronic device require precise control over the process parameters and the toolpath necessary to achieve a smoother and more refined surface suitable for functional. Further, to achieve the desired surface smoothness and integrity, post-processing steps, such as grinding, polishing, or precision machining, would be necessary that might improve the overall appearance of the component. Such finishing steps are not performed in this experiment. These may have introduced additional effects, which may have affected sensor performance.

8. Conclusion and Outlook

The presented investigations aim at bridging a perceived gap between sensor and manufacturing research communities, laying the foundation for future advancements in embedding

microdevices within metal, close to functional surfaces and tooling. Such integration of microdevices may enhance manufacturing processes with intelligent sensing capabilities.

While the high working temperatures of LMD pose a challenge, selecting process parameters carefully may preserve the functionality of embedded electronic devices.

Future research should focus on enhanced thermal protection of electronic devices, optimizing process parameters of LMD to minimize thermal impact on electronics while ensuring surface quality and improved deposition accuracy in particular for embedding microelectronic components.

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